

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-207-IG-20% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	20%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 207
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 10:24:12 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:49:41 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	4.887	602875	38.59	81349
2	6.119	176113	11.27	17349
3	7.409	616831	39.48	45568
4	14.113	166534	10.66	5335

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-204-IG-20% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221014
Vial:	10	Acq. Method Set:	20%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 204
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	17.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 1:56:23 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:53:28 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	4.861	15361171	95.21	1969228
2	6.119	488034	3.02	46553
3	7.413	111660	0.69	8249
4	14.219	173584	1.08	5445